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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE & ITS ROLE IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: In the future, intelligent machines will replace or enhance human capabilities in many areas. Artificial intelligence is the intelligence exhibited by machines or software. It is the subfield of computer science. Artificial intelligence is becoming popular in computer science as it has enhanced human life in many areas. Artificial intelligence in the last two decades has greatly improved the performance of the manufacturing, service sector, and so on in the field of education. Studies in the field of artificial intelligence have given rise to the rapidly growing technology known as expert systems. Artificial intelligence applications significantly impact various fields of life as the expert system is widely used these days to solve complex problems in various areas such as education, engineering, business, medicine, weather forecasting, etc. This study aims to explore the role of artificial intelligence applications in education. The study needs to be tested statistically for better understanding and to make the findings more generalised in the future.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), social robots (SR), smart learning (SL), education (E)

1.1 Introduction

Education is one of the most essential sectors of society. It is linked with all other sectors, and its impact on them is substantial. Due to this significance, education is indispensable for all cliques of society beyond any hurdles. For example, the challenge faced by the education sector during COVID-19 has been clear and appeals to many researchers. However, the societal challenges are not limited to such pandemics as some are always present; access to education, difficulties in reaching real classrooms, and financial issues are some of them. There are and will be many solutions to the problems; however, this study is focused on the solution that comes from technology in the form of artificial intelligence (AI). Artificial intelligence is changing every sector of society, and the education sector is no exception.

It is claimed that artificial intelligence is playing an increasing role in the research of educational technology, management sciences, and operational research areas. Intelligence is

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commonly considered as the ability to collect knowledge to solve complex problems. Shortly, intelligent machines will replace human capabilities in many places. Artificial intelligence is the study of intelligent machines and software that can reason, learn, gather knowledge, communicate, manipulate, and perceive objects.

In the present era, Students use smartphones to do their projects and use the available apps to gain knowledge of the different concepts and ideas. Videos, audio, and websites help students in their studies. AI tools are making the ideal environment for doing various computer courses. Sharing ideas, data, and slides is more straightforward than previously. Observations are present in education to transform the teaching methods from traditional to modern ones and leave the old way of writing on the blackboard. Students are encouraged to use modern AI tools to enhance their skills and make learning easier. The application of AI algorithms & systems in education is increasing, and researchers are using advanced AI techniques like data mining, deep mining, etc., to better deal with complex issues for the customised teaching of individual students. With the use of AI in education, schools may have faster classes in a shorter period. This century will require different thinking from the previous one.

2.1 Literature Review

Author Haseski H.I. (2019), in his research paper titled “What do Turkish pre-service teachers think about artificial intelligence”, briefly stated that the use of AI in education will create learning more individually, offer adequate learning understandings, permit students to determine their capacities, progress their creativeness and diminish teachers’ workload successively in these aspects that opposite views are also floating regarding the AI. Shifting the roles of teachers to computers is perceived as a risk in the studies on AI. Respective states and Nations are to create profiles of the concerned teachers to work on the support system of AI. The use of AI in education foresees major transformations in education systems and processes.

Authors Pedro et al. (2019), in their research paper titled “Artificial Intelligence in Education: Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Development”, highlighted that a new dual-type teacher model based on AI for individual education for teachers as AI would help these teachers reduce their time on the routine based works of administrative tasks. This ultimately allows teachers to concentrate on students for guidance and communication.

Authors Lijia Chen and Pingping Chen (2020), in their research paper titled “Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review”, suggested that AI is used in education differently. The development and innovation concluded in computers, machines, etc., have human characteristics based on ultimate decision-making abilities using adaptability and the learning process. AI is taking computer & computer-related technologies using embedded computer systems for transformation. The curriculum of the educational institutions has been customised & personalised using AI after shifting the educators from routine work to teaching activities. This is improving the learning activities of the students. Embedded systems have permitted the use of robots in educational institutions & chatbots to perform as teachers. It increases the efficiency and effectiveness of the system as it increases the quality of the instruction process.

2.2 Scope of Artificial Intelligence in the Field of Education

Artificial intelligence can automate basic activities in education, such as grading.

While AI may never be able to replace human grading, it’s getting close. It’s now possible for teachers to automate grading for nearly all kinds of multiple-choice and fill-in-the-blank testing, and

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automated grading of student writing may not be far behind. Today, essay-grading software is still in its infancy and not entirely up to par, yet in college, grading homework and tests for extensive lecture courses can be tedious work, even when TAs split it between them. Even in lower grades, teachers often find that grading takes up a significant amount of time, time that could be used to interact with students, prepare for class, or work on professional development.

Students could get additional support from AI tutors.

Some tutoring programs based on artificial intelligence already exist and can help students through basic mathematics, writing, and other subjects. These programs can teach students fundamentals, but they aren't ideal for helping students learn high-order thinking and creativity, something that real-world teachers are still required to facilitate. Yet that shouldn't rule out the possibility of AI tutors being able to do these things in the future. With the rapid pace of technological advancement that has marked the past few decades, advanced tutoring systems may not be a pipe dream.

It is altering how we find and interact with information.

Intelligent systems play a significant role in how we interact with information in our personal and professional lives and could change how we find and use information in schools and academia. Over the past few decades, AI-based systems have radically changed how we interact with information, and with newer, more integrated technology, students in the future may have vastly different experiences doing research and looking up facts than today's students.

AI can make trial-and-error learning less intimidating.

Trial and error is a critical part of learning, but failing or not knowing the answer is paralyzing for many students. Some don't like being put on the spot in front of their peers or authority figures like teachers. An intelligent computer system designed to help students learn is a much less daunting way to deal with trial and error. Artificial intelligence could offer students a way to experiment and learn in a relatively judgment-free environment, primarily when AI tutors can provide improvement solutions. AI is the perfect format for supporting this kind of learning, as AI systems often learn by a trial-and-error method.

AI-driven programs can give students and educators helpful feedback

AI can not only help teachers and students craft courses that are customised to their

Needs, but it can also provide feedback to both about the success of the course as a whole. Some schools, especially those with online offerings, are using AI systems to monitor student progress and to alert professors when there might be an issue with student performance. These AI systems allow students to get the support they need and for professors to find areas to improve instruction for students who struggle with the subject matter. However, AI programs at these schools aren't just offering advice on individual courses. Some are working to develop systems that can help students choose majors based on areas where they succeed and struggle. While students don't have to take the advice, it could mark a brave new world of college primary selection for future students.

Data powered by AI can change how schools find, teach, and support students.

Brilliant data gathering, powered by intelligent computer systems, is changing how colleges interact with prospective and current students. From recruiting to helping students choose the best courses, smart computer systems are helping make every part of the college experience more closely tailored to student needs and goals. Data mining systems are integral in today's higher-ed landscape, but

artificial intelligence could further alter higher education. Initiatives are already underway at some schools to offer students AI-guided training that can ease the transition between college and high school. Who knows, but the college selection process may end up like Amazon or Netflix, with a system recommending the best schools and programs for student interests.

2.3 Scope of Artificial Intelligence in Different Areas

Language understanding:

The ability to "understand" and respond to the natural language. To translate from a spoken language to a written form and to translate from one natural language to another natural language.

- Speech Understanding
- Question Answering
- Information Retrieval
- Language Translation

Games

The ability to accept a formal set of rules for games such as Chess, Go, Kalah, Checkers, etc., and to translate these rules into a representation or structure that allows problem-solving and learning abilities to be used in reaching an adequate level of performance.

Learning and adaptive systems:

The ability to adapt behaviour based on previous experience and to develop general rules concerning the world based on such knowledge.

- Cybernetics
- Concept Formation

Problem-solving

Ability to formulate a problem in a suitable representation, to plan for its solution, and to know when new information is needed and how to obtain it.

- Inference (Resolution-Based Theorem Proving, Plausible Inference and Inductive Inference)
- Interactive Problem Solving
- Automatic Program Writing
- Heuristic Search

Robots

A combination of most or all of the above abilities with the ability to move over terrain and manipulate objects.

- Exploration
- Transportation/Navigation
- Industrial Automation (e.g., Process Control, Assembly Tasks, Executive Tasks)
- Security
- Other (Agriculture, Fishing, Mining, Sanitation, Construction, etc.)
- Military

For Entertainment

We can apply artificial intelligence to the world of music, make artificial directors who see the real world, and generate stories. We can make robots that compose music and pitch, and robots can create your favourite songs. New technology can also restore to life stars who are dead, like Tupac Shakur and Michael Jackson.

3.1 Drawbacks

It is found that the following are the drawbacks as listed:

- Lacking intuitive knowledge and supporting mechanical thinking
- Pragmatic views rather than humanistic values
- Human intervention less in education
- Lack of data security or uncontrolled intelligence technologies
- Destroyed social relationships
- Information orientation human nature

4.1 The Future of AI

Many experts are doing research in the field of Artificial intelligence, and in the future, machines will become more and more powerful. However, anything with advantages also has disadvantages, so there can be ethical issues related to machines. For example, if any machine is made for very sensitive work and makes any mistake, then who will be responsible? If an AI program is made for diagnosis purposes and gives the wrong answer, we cannot claim the doctor for it. So, for it, policy will have to be made. In the future, such machines will be developed which will communicate with us the same as humans and be able to guess what should be done in which situation.

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, AI has influenced many sectors, and education is one of them. It is a contemporary method of tutoring or teaching and learning that can address and resolve many learning-related issues. It can fix issues like content accessibility and teacher deficiency, where students can learn without stress or impacting others. AI implementation and adoption are unavoidable in the education sector. AI technologies are not limited to innovative learning, tutoring systems, and social robots; many other intelligent technologies, such as virtual facilitators, online learning environments, learning management systems, and learning analytics, contribute significantly to the sector. AI produces an environment of personalised learning systems for students with the help of tools. AI will support the progress in education for optimum learning and assist the teachers in the regular management work. It is suggested that uncontrolled, excessive, and inappropriate use of mobile phones is causing social, behavioural and affective problems. There are fewer places for teachers and more for robots after the implementation of AI in education. Displacement of jobs will be more likely in the area of teaching. AI means eliminating jobs for the people concerned.

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